

REPORT:

A1.1.3: Using the Database/inventory for flow control components

Work package 1

<https://mfmet.eu>

This report was written as part of activity A1.1.3 from the EMPIR Establishing Metrology Standards in Microfluidic Devices (MFMET) project. The three-year European project commenced on 1st June 2021 and focused on providing a generic methodology of accurate measurement of a particular quantity in a microfluidic device by utilising standardised methods and reference documents, e.g. VIM & GUM. For more details about this project, please visit <https://mfmet.eu>

This report was written by:

Name	Institution	e-mail
Thomas Schrøder Daugbjerg	Danish Technological Institute	<i>tsda@teknologisk.dk</i>
Vania Silverio	INESC MN	<i>vania.silverio@tecnico.ulisboa.pt</i>

The EMPIR initiative is co-funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and the EMPIR Participating States

Contents

1. Scope.....	3
2. Introduction	3
3. Description of the database.....	3
4. Manual for using the database	6
4.1. Roles.....	6
4.2. Access and URLs.....	6
4.3. Creating a new User.....	7
4.3.1. Actions by the User	7
4.3.2. Assign Admin role to a Client	7
4.3.3. Actions by an Admin	7
4.4. User login	8
4.5. Viewing database entries.....	8
4.6. Creating database entries.....	9
4.7. Update database entries.....	9
4.8. Deleting database entries	9
4.9. Remove nodes in the database.....	10
4.10. Exporting database content.....	10
4.11. Link to the webpage of MFMET	10
5. Discussion and conclusion	10
References	10

1. Scope

This document is a report that documents the implementation of a database made for activity A1.1.3 of the project MFMET. It also describes the relationship of the database to the previous activities A1.1.1 and A1.1.2, which compiled information on microfluidic components and definitions. Finally, it provides a manual on how a User could interact with the database, for example to create new entries and look up microfluidic components.

A1.1.3 M13	Using input from A1.1.1 and A1.1.2, DTI, INESC MN, TUBITAK and BHT will develop a database/inventory for flow control components containing base operating principles (internal flow control, external flow control), family of components, and types and subtypes of components.	DTI, INESC MN, TUBITAK, BHT
---------------	---	--------------------------------

2. Introduction

In the MFMET project, activity A1.1.1 compiled a report of existing equipment and components in microfluidics (Kartmann et al., 2022). Furthermore, activity A1.1.2 compiled vocabulary for the concepts and definitions of flow control in microfluidics (Silverio et al., 2022).

Deriving from needs identified by the Microfluidics Supply Chain (e.g. collected in surveys from the Microfluidics Association or from the MFMET project), Activity A1.1.3 aims to use the knowledge compiled in activities A1.1.1 and A1.1.2 and produce a database with an inventory for flow control components. The database intends to present the flow control components along with information such as basic operating principles, family of components and types and subtypes of components. It is a goal of the database to create an interactive and efficient overview of information on flow control components.

3. Description of the database

The database is developed and hosted by the internally built software platform YoDa at the Danish Technological Institute (DTI). YoDa is an abbreviation for *your data*. YoDa is a software environment for development, version control, testing and production, and can host webservices. YoDo accepts code written in TypeScript, and it can be used to build web solutions for databases, data acquisition, data visualization and more. Thus, Clients (Users or Administrators/Admins) of the database for MFMET activity A1.1.3 can recognize the words *yoda* and *teknologisk* in the URL used to interact with the database (<https://yoda.teknologisk.dk/MFMET-database>). The Clients can interact with the database by typing in the URL in a web browser, to see the webservice with a Graphical User Interface. Section 4 explains in more detail how to access the database and how to use it.

Figure 1 shows an overview of the design of the database. The database has five classes which are inspired by the layout of microfluidic components found in the report from activity A1.1.1 (Kartmann et al., 2022). Each class has a tree structure of properties that lists the properties system, flow characteristics, mechanical characteristics, and sub properties of these.

Figure 1: Overview of the design of the database. Notice the database has five classes: flow generator, flow sensor, pressure sensor, manual dispensers and valves, and finally flow control components and accessories. Each class has a tree structure of properties and sub properties. All classes have similar structure and fields for harmonization.

Table 1 shows examples of data from the database, which is formatted using *json* format. In Table 1 one may recognize the tree structure of classes with properties and sub properties also illustrated in Figure 1.

Table 1: Examples of the data of the database formatted with the json format. Notice the five data classes and their properties and sub properties. The data structures match the classes and properties presented in Figure 1.

```

{
  "title": "MFMET Instrument Database ",
  "formatversion": "1.0.0",
  "flowGeneration": [
    {
      "flowCharacteristics": {
        "range": [
          500,
          9000000
        ],
        "responceTime": "",
        "stability": [
          10,
          1000
        ],
        "unit": "µL/h"
      },
      "mechanicalCharacteristics": {
        "connections": {
          "size": "1/3",
          "type": "swagelok",
          "unit": "inch"
        },
        "pressure": {
          "range": [
            1,
            2
          ],
          "unit": "Bar"
        }
      },
      "system": {
        "manufacturer": "Tecan",
        "model": "Cavro XLP 6000",
        "type": "syringe"
      }
    }
  ],
  "flowMeasurement": [
    {
      "flowCharacteristics": {
        "range": [
          1,
          1
        ],
        "responceTime": "",
        "stability": [
          1,
          2
        ],
        "unit": "µL/min"
      },
      "mechanicalCharacteristics": {
        "connections": {
          "size": "",
          "type": "",
          "unit": ""
        },
        "pressure": {
          "range": [
            1,
            2
          ],
          "unit": "mBar"
        }
      },
      "system": {
        "manufacturer": "Sartorius",
        "model": "MSU 6.6S",
        "type": "Gravemetric"
      }
    }
  ],
  "pressureSensor": [
    {
      "flowCharacteristics": {
        "range": [
          1,
          1
        ],
        "responceTime": "",
        "stability": [
          1,
          2
        ],
        "unit": "µL/min"
      },
      "mechanicalCharacteristics": {
        "connections": {
          "size": "",
          "type": "",
          "unit": ""
        },
        "pressure": {
          "range": [
            1,
            2
          ],
          "unit": "mBar"
        }
      },
      "system": {

```

```

    "manufacturer": "Sartorius",
    "model": "MSU 6.6S",
    "type": "Membrane"
  }
},
"manualDispensersAndValves": [
  {
    "flowCharacteristics": {
      "range": [
        1,
        1
      ],
      "responseTime": "",
      "stability": [
        1,
        2
      ],
      "unit": "µL/min"
    },
    "mechanicalCharacteristics": {
      "connections": {
        "size": "",
        "type": "",
        "unit": ""
      },
      "pressure": {
        "range": [
          1,
          2
        ],
        "unit": "mBar"
      }
    },
    "system": {
      "manufacturer": "Sartorius",
      "model": "MSU 6.6S",
      "type": "Membrane"
    }
  }
],
"flowControlComponentsAndAccessories": [
  {
    "flowCharacteristics": {
      "range": [
        1,
        1
      ],
      "responseTime": "",
      "stability": [
        1,
        2
      ],
      "unit": "µL/min"
    },
    "mechanicalCharacteristics": {
      "connections": {
        "size": "0.1",
        "type": "swagelok",
        "unit": "mm"
      },
      "pressure": {
        "range": [
          1,
          2
        ],
        "unit": "kPa"
      }
    },
    "system": {
      "manufacturer": "swagelok",
      "model": "",
      "type": "ss"
    }
  }
]
}
}

```

4. Manual for using the database

4.1. Roles

Anyone with a web browser and access to the internet can to access the webservice of the database as a Client. A Client of the webservice can take one of two roles: User or Admin. Depending on the role, a Client will have different options in the Graphical User Interface of the webservice.

4.2. Access and URLs

A Client with the role User, who wishes to view, create, or export database entries, is to access the webservice of the database through the URL <https://yoda.teknologisk.dk/MFMET-database>

A Client with the role Admin, who wishes to add Users or Admins, is to access the webservice of the database through the URL <https://apps.teknologisk.dk/app-management>

A Client with the role of Admin, who wishes to delete database entries, is to access the webservice of the database through the URL <https://yoda.teknologisk.dk/MFMET-Admin>

4.3. Creating a new User

4.3.1. Actions by the User

To create a new User for the webservice of the database the Client must access the URL <https://yoda.teknologisk.dk/MFMET-database>. The Client should see the login screen and click “New User”. The Client is presented with a form, which requests the **full name** and the **e-mail address** of the User. After clicking “Create User” an e-mail with a new link is sent to the e-mail address stated by the User requesting to choose a password. The User must input the password. The Client has now created a User for the webservice of the database.

Returning to the link, above this paragraph, the Client may log in using the credentials: e-mail and password.

When logging in for the first time, the User will view the database entries, but cannot yet create database entries. This is because the webservice of the database only allows creation of database entries for Users that have been previously approved by an Admin. The next subsection explains how an Admin can approve a User.

4.3.2. Assign Admin role to a Client

To assign an Admin role to a Client of the webservice of the database, a Client (with the role of Admin) must access the URL <https://apps.teknologisk.dk/app-management>

The Client is presented with a login screen, and if with an Admin role, it can login. The Admin is then presented with two buttons: “^/MFMET-Admin” and “^/MFMET-database”.

Clicking “^/MFMET-Admin” the Admin is presented with a list of e-mails of Users with Admin role. The Admin can assign the role of Admin to a Client by clicking “Add User to endpoint”, entering the e-mail address, and clicking OK. The Client’s e-mail should then have been added to the list. The Admin can also remove the role of Admin from a Client by clicking the red cross after the respective e-mail address and clicking OK.

4.3.3. Actions by an Admin

To approve a User role to a Client of the webservice to create database entries, another Client (with the role of Admin) must access the URL <https://apps.teknologisk.dk/app-management>

The Client is presented with a login screen, and if with an Admin role, it can login. The Admin is then presented with two buttons: “^/MFMET-Admin” and “^/MFMET-database”.

Clicking “^/MFMET-database” the Admin is presented with a list of e-mails for approved Users. The Admin can approve a User’s permission to create database entries by clicking “Add User to endpoint”, entering the e-mail address of the User, and clicking OK. The User’s e-mail should now have been added the list. The Admin can also remove the permission of a User to create database entries by clicking the red cross after the respective e-mail address and clicking OK.

4.4. User login

A User may go to the URL <https://yoda.teknologisk.dk/MFMET-database>

Here the User can log in using the credentials: e-mail and password, which were used when creating the User.

- If the login is successful the User should see a Graphical User Interface of the webservice of the database, which enables viewing the database content.
- If the User is approved by an Admin and the login is successful, the User should see a Graphical User Interface of the webservice of the database, which enables viewing and creating database entries.

Notice that the log in dialogue also has functionality for forgotten password.

4.5. Viewing database entries

Viewing database entries, prerequires that the User is successfully logged in.

For a logged in User that is not approved for creating entries in the database, the webservice of the database has two options for subpages. To view database entries, make sure the subpage "Overview" is selected, or select it by clicking on it.

The "Overview" subpage has one single dropdown menu under the text "Choose class". Click the dropdown menu and choose among one of the five classes of microfluidic components: "Flow generator", "Flow sensor", "Pressure sensor", "Manual dispensers and valves", and "Flow control components and accessories" (see Figure 1).

After choosing the class the table shows all database entries of that class. Notice the search field, which can perform a search for matches in all columns. Figure 2 shows a simple process flow diagram for viewing database entries.

Figure 2: A simple process flow diagram for viewing database entries.

4.6. Creating database entries

To create database entries, the User must be logged in and approved for creating database entries by an Admin. If these conditions are fulfilled, the webservice of the database has 3 options for subpages. To create database entries, make sure the subpage "Database input" is selected, or select it by clicking on it.

The User should then see a Graphical User Interface where it is possible to create a new entry for a new instrument in the database. When giving input, one must choose between distinct options from drop down menus, or type in text or numbers in input fields. Moving from left to right, top to bottom, examples of input are classes, types, manufacturer, range, and many more. Input fields that expect a certain format have validation of input, and these fields reject invalid input. Furthermore, some input fields have help from grey text with examples, and there can be further help from the question mark symbols if the mouse cursor is positioned above these.

If all necessary inputs are filled in, and all inputs are valid, one can click the button "Create instrument in the database" and the input will create a new entry in the database. *Figure 3* shows a simple process flow diagram for creating database entries.

Figure 3: A simple process flow diagram for creating database entries.

4.7. Update database entries

There is no functionality for Users or Admins to update or edit existing entries in the database.

4.8. Deleting database entries

There is no functionality for Users to delete entries in the database.

4.9. Remove nodes in the database

A Client with the role of an Admin can access the URL <https://yoda.teknologisk.dk/MFMET-Admin>

Here the Admin can log in and be presented with a nodes and tree-structure view of all database entries.

The node of a specific database entry can be identified, and if the square symbol of the entry is clicked the Admin is presented with another menu with the option to remove the node by clicking “Remove”. After “Remove” has been clicked, confirm the deletion by clicking the button “Save changes” located at the bottom of the web page. If you leave the webpage without clicking save changes, the deletion will not be executed.

4.10. Exporting database content

Exporting the database content prerequisites that the User is approved by an Admin and logged in.

The webservice of the database has 3 options for subpages. To export the database content, make sure the subpage “Overview” is selected, or select it by clicking on it.

On the subpage “Overview” there is a button with the text “Export all data”. When clicked the browser downloads a text file formatted as tabulator separated values (tsv), which contains all entries of the database. Having this file, the User can access the content of the database in other contexts.

4.11. Link to the webpage of MFMET

Using the link to the MFMET webpage, prerequisites that the User is approved by an Admin and logged in.

The webservice of the database has 3 options for subpages. To use the link to the MFMET webpage click on the subpage heading “MFMET.eu”, and a new browser tab opens with the MFMET webpage.

5. Discussion and conclusion

The database can be a tool for the partners of the MFMET project, to compile a comprehensive inventory of microfluidic components. As of early 2023, there are no plans to remove the database from the YoDa platform, and it may stay online well into the foreseeable future. In any event, the ability to download the database content as a text file, will enable the compiled inventory to live on in other contexts, outside the database.

References

Kartmann, S., van Heeren, H., Batista, E., Akselli, B., & Silverio, V. (2022). *MFMET A1.1.1 Literature and market research: definitions, characteristics, specifications, application and function of flow control components*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.6841323>

Silverio, V., Metaxiotou, Z., Batista, E., Kartmann, S., Oghard, F., & Lötters, J. (2022). *MFMET A1.1.2 - Definitions Symbols and Vocabulary of Flow Control*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.7092031>